

ISic1227

I.Sicily inscription 1227

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

volcanic

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140713

1. Ἀσκληπιῶ
2. καὶ Ὑγείᾳ
3. σωτηῆρσιν
4. πολιούχοις.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492833

EDCS 39101593

PHI 140713

Bibliography

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